

13 May 1973.

Dear Andrew,

I've seen C-K who was interested in what happened in
Omran and I believe interested in carrying on. He did
not know whether he could afford to dig at Dasht-e-Neh
or not yet. Generally I felt he would like to, but he is
in difficulties over vehicles and cannot decide until they
are viewed out.

Saw Martha and warned her you were planting
a garden and therefore it was no good going to Oxford
if she wanted a rest. She seemed reasonably pleased
with prospects for the summer except that vehicles and
permits were problems.

Half the world seems to be going to Yabuya this summer.
It should be interesting!

I will, inshallah, get back one of the black & white
prints and the duplicate negative you wanted tomorrow
and will mail them immediately. The other print is held
until Evelyn gets here as I had sent in the same negative
for a print to show C-K. I'll get it off to you as soon as
possible.

I would like to send small collections of pictures -
russat, to about half dozen people including Historical
Association, apart from pictures accompanying reports.
I hope to have mine and Dudley's side ready by June!

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would hope you and I can put the whole thing together
in first week of June. I thought following ought to get
pictures Peysters

C. Maxwell

J. Townsend

D. Small

R. Jacelli

Historical Assoc.

J. Jennings

Should know as Dir. General of CIA,
Should know personally.

Have you heard anything about the study collect-
of pottery and whether it can go to Harvard?

Hope all well with you and that you get your
back.

Yours

Jim.